

Drainage System and Ground water quality in Basti Municipality Area (U.P.) : A composite study

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Abstract

In the developing countries like India, where population density is high and has enormous population growth during the last few decades due to high migration in urban areas and have a lot of issues about uncontrolled and inappropriate development. Population increases results in more urbanization, more impervious area, and less infiltration and greater surface runoff, change in topographical and drainage profile, increasing the flow of water in proportion to the urbanization rate. Indian cities are expanding outwards in the fringes of the cities, engulfing several natural features like forests, water bodies, and agricultural land, transforming the cities into urban agglomerations. These urban agglomerations have numerous issue and problems which aggravates the quality of life. Ground water is the main source of raw water for water supply to the municipality area of Basti. Therefore, it is imperative to understand the relationship of for urban waste water flow and its plausible impacts on the ground water quality in cities. The paper finds some convincing link between two.

Key words: Basti Municipal Area, Water Quality, Drainage System

INTRODUCTION

Human activities along with natural processes have radically altered the earth's surface, oceans, and atmosphere, especially over the past 200 years [1]. Growing human population densities, intensified land-use, invasive species, often linked to changes in habitat heterogeneity, increasing habitat fragmentation and limited dispersal capacities are threatening ecosystems world-wide and protected areas are often the only refuge for endangered species. Indeed, the effects of these factors on protected areas can be further amplified by changing climatic conditions [2,3]. Humans have altered ecosystems more rapidly and extensively than ever, largely to meet rapidly growing demands for resources along with economic development. These demands along with unorganised human settlement have been considered important drivers of ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss [4].

Humans have long been used air, land and water resources as 'sinks' into which we dispose of the wastes we generate. These disposal practices leave most wastes inadequately treated, thereby causing groundwater contamination. Water is most vital liquid for maintaining the life on the earth. About 97% water is exists in oceans that is not suitable for drinking and only 3% is fresh water wherein 2.97% is comprised by glaciers and ice caps and remaining little portion of 0.3% is available as a surface and ground water for human use [5]. The major cause of water contamination is high growth of population, expansion in industries, throwing away of waste water and chemical effluents into drains and other water sources [6]. The removal, destruction or impairment of natural ecosystems are among the greatest causes of critical impacts on the sustainability of our natural water resources.

Drainage is an important infrastructure in urban development, if urban development is not well planned, it can bring negative effects [7]. Most domestic and industrial waste water discharges are not processed and directly enter drainage system. Wastewater (domestic as well as industrial) that flows in the drainage eventually enters the water body. This issue has become one of the major factors causing river and ground water pollution. This pollution occurs due to the poor waste water

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discharge system, considering that in general the drainage system in Basti City is multipurpose, either to drain rain water or as household domestic waste water [7]. The multi-function properties of these drainage can ultimately affect the final effluent in the river and ground water. Water quality issues have become increasingly important, due to pollutants from urban areas being washed in to rivers or the ground water. Traditional drainage systems cannot easily control poor runoff quality and may contribute to the problem. There for, present study initiated with an aim to find correlation between existing drainage system and ground water quality of the Basti Municipal Area.

STUDY AREA

Basti was originally known as Vaishishthi. The origin of the name Vaishishthi is attributed to the fact that this area was the ashram of Rishi (sage) Vashistha in ancient period. Rama with his younger brother Lakshmana had been here for some time with Rishi Vashistha [8]. Presently, Basti is a city, municipal board and commissionaire of the Uttar Pradesh. Basti district is a part of Basti division. The district lies between the parallels of 26° 23' and 27° 30' North Latitude and 82° 17' and 83° 20' East longitude.

The total area is 2688 sq. Km with a population of 24,64,464 as per 2011 census. The density of Basti district for 2011 is 916 people per sq. km. The district is bounded by river Ghaghra in south and Ameer in north. Its maximum length from north to south is about 75 km. and breadth from east to west about 70km. The district lies between Sant Kabir Nagar on the east and Gonda on the west. On the south, the Ghaghra river separates it from the Faizabad and newly created district named Ambedkar Nagar. While on the North it is bounded by district Siddharth Nagar. It is head-quarter of Basti commissionery (Basti, Sant Kabir Nager & Siddharth Nagar). Although entire district represents a flat topography, but can be divided topographically into several distinct tracts namely, the low land of the Ghaghra in the south (khadar), extending from that river to its tributary, the Kuwana; the central upland, between the latter river and the Rapti; and the low and ill-drained paddy belt between the Rapti and the Nepal boundary [9].

The district experiences great climatic variation. Summers are long, from early April to October, with intervening monsoon seasons. Cold waves from the Himalayan region shudders entire district in the winter, from December to February. The temperature ranges between 9°C to 20°C in winter & 25°C to 44°C in summers. Fog is common in the winters, while hot dry wind, called loo, blows in summers. The district receives a normal rain fall of 1169.80 mm; with ground water availability 106048 ham, & experiences a sub-humid climate. Being located in the plains of Ganga, the soil is consisting of old as well as new alluvium with kankar & reh, and is fertile because low level floods regularly replenish it. So, the most important profession is agriculture & hence agrarian economy [8].

After the formation of two more districts from Basti District (Sant Kabir Nager & Siddharth Nagar), the city municipality area witnessed a sharp and significant increase in population density. Basti Sadar (City) is stretched south-west to north-east ward in approx. 8 km length with a width of approx. 3.5 km, (area approx. 25 Km²), with a population density of 4818. This area is under Basti Nager-Palika Parishad. Changes in land use can also have an impact on the quality of raw water sources and have implications for the allocation of water use for communities [10]. The increasing population exert presser on the basic amenities of city dwellers. The drainage system of the area is facing many challenges and become a potential problem for water quality.

RELIEF AND WATER FLOW

The Basti municipality area is situated at higher altitude than its surrounding. The Amhat ghat region in the south-west direction is about 91-93 meter above the sea level and on the other side the height of the railway station area (in the north-east) is about 91meters. The central and north-

central part of the municipal area is comparatively lower (85-90 meters), due to which the water flows here and goes to low laying areas on both sides.

CURRENT STATUS OF DRAINAGE

The Basti municipal area is divided in to 25 wards (1. Mishraualia, 2. Narhariya, 3. Purana Dakkhana, 4. Murlijot, 5. Pandey Bazar, 6. Turkahiya, 7. Pikaoura Shivgula, 8. Surti Hatta, 9. Pikaoura Datturai, 10. Chikwa Tola, 11. Rauta Par, 12. Mali Tola, 13. Pathan Tola, 14. Company Bagh, 15. Gargodiya, 16. Bairihwa, 17. Rameshwer Puri, 18. Etaliya, 19. Belwadandi, 20. Pikaoura Bux, 21. Vishun Purva, 22. Avas Vikas, 23. Katra, 24. Mahrikhawa & 25. Ori Jot).

The drainage system mainly consists of Three major and two minor drains. All the water of Basti Nagar Palik area comes out of the city through five major drains. The first one of these drains passes through the Turkahia locality of the Gandhi Nagar area of the city and joins the Kuwano river through the south-west border of the city. The total length is 1900 meters. The second major drain crosses the Malviya Road from near the municipal council building and reaches the Gadhadhakhori locality and joins the Baherwa drain coming from yhe market. From where these two drains flow out to the north eastern boundary of the city. The total length of this drain is 2600 meters. The third drain falls behind the GVM Convent School, passing through the fish market located on the station road of the city. In this drain the water of Mangal Bajar and Dakshin Darwaz and the surrounding area falls. The length of this drain is 500 meters. The rest two drains of 350 meters (from Hospital Chauraha to munderwa road) and 600 meters (from overhead water tank, Katara to IIT gate) are presently obstructed. It resulted water-logging in this area during rainy seasons [11].

The nine small drains had been constructed by Basti Nagar Palika Parishad to channelise water from the 25 wards to major drains. The important ones are, a 3100-meter sewer(from Roadways to Company Bagh), a 4800-meter sewer(from Roadways to Company Bagh through Rauta Chauraha), which finally drains near Jail Road. Another 2400-meter sewer is present in the station road which runs from station road to Mangal Bajar to Karuababa Chauraha, and collect sewage from adjoining areas. Besides these, there are numbers of small drains are located in the streets of each ward, through which sewage possess to major drains. But the condition of these small drains is not good (Fig 4).

The nature of drainage can be divided in to three parts [11]:

(A) Areas with Drainage Accessibility

The drainage system in Gandhi Nagar and adjoining area is in good condition. The water from this area flows in to major drain, passing through Gandhi Nagar. This area is comparatively higher, so water rain water stagnation is very low in this area. This area consists of ward number 14-Company Bagh, 17-Rameshwer Puri, 20-Pikaoura Bux, 21-Vishun Purva and 25-Ori Jot.

(B) Areas with Obstructed Drainage

Although, Basti city area is bestowed with proper drainage, but due to negligence of the employees and the local peoples, water drainage is in poor condition in some areas. City dwellers often dispose their garbage's in the drain, thereby choked drains. These areas include some parts of ward number 24- Mahrikhawa, 22-Avas Vikas, some portions of ward number 16-Bairihwa, 6-Turkahiya, major part of 9-Pikaoura Datturai, 4-Murlijot, 15-Gargodiya and major portion of 2-Narhariya.

(C) Areas without proper drainage

In some wards of the municipal area either there are no proper drainage systems available or in damaged state. These areas include ward number 3-Purana Dakkhana, some parts of 16-Bairihwa, 11-Rauta Par, 8- Surti Hatta, 10-Chikwa Tola, 1-Mishraualia, 5-Pandey Bazar etc.

STATUS OF GROUND WATER QUALITY

Groundwater is used by about two billion people worldwide; making it the single most used natural resource. The estimated annual production of groundwater is between 600 and 700 cubic kilometers (billion cubic meters). It is believed that groundwater is purer and safer than surface water due to earth mantle covering. Presence of more than 200 chemical constituents in groundwater has been documented including approximately 175 organic and more than 50 inorganic and radio nucleotides. Along with human activities, water quality is affected by a combination of natural processes.

In the developing countries, contamination of water supplies by inorganic chemicals contamination, poor sanitary conditions and illness brought about by pathogenic organisms is of major concern. Water is drawn from the ground for a variety of uses, principally community water supply, farming (both livestock and irrigated cultivation) and industrial processes. Water for drinking should be free of disease-causing microorganisms, harmful chemicals, objectionable taste and odour problems, and excessive levels of colour and suspended material. Ideally the quality of the water should not impair its myriad other general amenity uses.

The results of ground water study revealed that the groundwaters of the Basti Municipal area are had higher total dissolved solids, hardness, alkalinity, chloride, magnesium and presence of *E. coli* in the groundwater (Table- 1) and people are at danger of various health risks [9]. The high concentration of TDS, water loses its potability and reduces the solubility of oxygen in water. High magnesium hardness is common problem with in the study area. That is the main causes of encrustation in water and scale in utensils. The presence of coliforms in water is alarming situation from the Public Health point of view. people are at risk of various health risks

DISCUSSION

The unsatisfactory drainage system in some localities of Basti municipal area and alarming situations of ground water quality, underlines their nexus and complex inter-relationship[12]. Ground water contamination is nearly always the result of human activity. In areas where population density is high and human use of the land is intensive (like Basti municipal area), ground water is especially vulnerable. Depending on its physical, chemical, and biological properties, a contaminant that has been released into the environment may move within an aquifer in the same manner that ground water moves. Soils that are porous and permeable tend to transmit water and certain types of contaminants with relative affluence to an aquifer below. The unjudicial pumping of ground water in the area, further aggravate the contamination problem, because water from the zone of contribution, is drawn into the well and the surrounding aquifer.

One of the main causes of ground water contamination in the Basti municipal area is the effluent (outflow) from septic tanks, drains etc. Approximately three-fourth of all homes in the municipal area rely on septic systems to dispose of their human wastes. Although each individual system releases a relatively small amount of waste into the ground, the large number and widespread use of these systems makes them a serious contamination source. Septic systems that are improperly sited, designed, constructed, or maintained can contaminate ground water with bacteria, viruses, nitrates, detergents, oils, and chemicals [13].

The apathic attitude and unhealthy civic sense of inhabitant, pose another challenge in this front. The disposal of household waste and effluents in drainage system, and their choked status, further aggravate the problem. The stagnated water percolate to the ground water aquifer, mix various organic/inorganic components produced through disintegration of waste and effluents in drainage system, particularly in the water logged densely populated old settlement areas.

Fig. 1 Study area

Fig. 2 Drainage map pf municipal area

Fig. 3 Wards map pf municipal area

Table-1

Comparative status of Physico-chemical parameters of Basti municipal area are with Indian Standard Drinking Water – Specification [9]

S. No.	Indian Standard Drinking Water – Specification (BIS 10500 : 1983,1991)			Physico-chemical parameters in Basti municipal area		
	Parameter	Desirable Limit	Permissible Limit	Minimum	Maximum	Mean value
1.	Temperature (°C)			25.1	30.3	26.9 - 28.9
2.	pH	6.5-8.5	No relaxation	6.82	8.42	7.01- 8.08
3.	T.D.S. (mg/L)	500	2000	230	1060	260.0 - 906.6
4.	Conductance (m mhos/cm)	0.30	1.50	0.36	1.64	0.40 – 1.43
5.	Alkalinity (mg/L)	200	600	115	411	124.0 – 404.3
6.	Hardness (mg/L)	300	600	156	646	158.6 – 464.6
7.	Free CO ₂			2.0	38.0	4.3 – 24.3
8.	Chloride (mg/L)	250	1000	0.01	0.42	0.01 – 0.34
9.	Chloride (Residual) (mg/L)	0.2	1.0	1.06	9.94	2.09 – 5.32
10.	Sulphide (mg/L)	Below detectable limit	-	32.3	195.5	56.1 – 151.7
11.	Phosphate (µg/l)	-		3.7	7.5	
12.	Fluoride (µg/l)	1000	1500	3.0	20.70	
13.	Calcium (mg/L)	Up to 200	-	4.81	160.32	38.28 – 83.38
14.	Magnesium (mg/L)	Up to 100	-	67.90	485.68	117.5 – 381.2
15.	Iron (µg/l)	300	1000	17.8	76.2	
16.	Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	Min. 6.0	-	1.6	7.6	3.4 – 6.5
17.	B.O.D. (mg/L)	Max. 2.0	-	0.2	2.6	0.2 – 2.6
18.	E. coli (in100 ml)	Nil	No relaxation	nil	40	

CONCLUSION

In the Basti municipal area, water logging and inefficient drainage is a common problem. Mode of sewage disposal and soak pit toilets aggravate the problem further. The potability of ground water is in question. The mechanism of mingling of logged surface water with ground water aquifers need further study. Bacterial contamination should be properly addressed and disinfected before being used for drinking purpose. A comprehensive sewerage system is demand of time, along with safe disposal of wastes in the area. The collaborative role of Municipal authorities, Local

Administration, Public Health Department and Jal Nigam is need of hour to safeguard groundwater quality in the study area.

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